

PRODUCTION OF BACTERIOCIN USING LACTIC ACID BATERIAL ISOLATED FROM FERMENTED FUFU.

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Abstract

Bacteriocins are antimicrobial agents produced by bacteria which are very useful in food preservation and in medicine. This study evaluated bacteriocin produced by lactic acid bacteria isolated from fermenting fufu. Overall five (5) isolates were identified to belong to the genus lactobacillus. The lactobacillus species were inoculated into MRS Broth, centrifuged to separate the cells from the supernatant. The supernatants were used against food spoilage and pathogenic organisms by agar well diffusion method for bacteriocin production. It was discovered that only 5 Lactobacillus Spp produced bacteriocin against the test organisms. Staphylococcus aureus was sensitive to 3 proteus 4, Pseudomonas 5, Escherichia coli 4 while Klebsiella Spp, Salmonella typhi and bacillus Spp were all resistant to the lactobacillus speicies.

Key Words: *Bacteriocin, Lactic Acid, Fermented Fufu*

INTRODUCTION

Microorganisms compete for the limited space and nutrient present in natural ecological niche. Therefore, they have developed several strategies in order to survive; production of antimicrobial agent such as bacteriocin is one of them. Gram positive bacteria and mainly lactic acid bacteria (LAB) are being increasingly studied for their production of bacteriaocin like substance. (Heng *et al.*; 2007). Bacteriocins are ribosomally synthesized antimicrobial peptides widely distributed in nature. This peptide biodiversity is supported by several differences in their structure (Drider *et al.*, 2006). Most characterized bacteriocin are heat stable, non-toxic and susceptible to degradation by proteolytic enzymes present in the gastrointestinal tract. (Abriouel *et al.*, 2003).

Many bacteriocins are active against food- borne pathogens especially listerialmonocytogens (Vignolo *et al.*, 1996). Several types of bacteriocins from food- associated lactic acid bacteria have been identified and characterized of which the important ones are Nisin, diplococcic, acidophilin, bulgaricin, helveticins, lactacins and plant aricins. (Nettles and Bare foot, 1993). Other bacteriocins of lactobacilli have been reported to be effective against closely related species of mesophilic lactobacillvs and therefore considered as potential natural food preservatives (Daeschel,1993; De Vuyst and vandamme, 1994).

The increasing consumption of food containing additives with preservatives and consumers concerns have created a higher demand for more natural and minimally processed foods. Therefore, there is a high interest in

naturally produced antimicrobial agents that interest and also the potential applications in health care sectors have attracted the interest of academia and industry research on bacteriocin production purification genetics and application. Therefore, keeping in view the above this work will focus on the following aims and objectives

1.1 AIM AND OBJECTIVES: The aim of this research work is to use bacteriocin from lactic acid bacteria for screening against selected organisms.

The objectives of the study include:

- a) To isolate lactic acid bacteria from fermenting fufu.
- b) To produce bacteriocin from bacteria isolated from fermenting fufu.
- c) To test the bacteriocin on the selected organisms.

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 LACTIC ACID BACTERIA (LAB)

Lactic acid bacteria are a group of gram- positive bacteria linked to a constellation of morphological metabolic and physiological characteristics. They are included in the group of non-spore forming, non respiring cocci or rods, catalase negative, devoid of cytochromes, non-aerobic but aero-tolerant, fastidious, acid tolerant and strictly fermentative with lactic acid as the major and product during the fermentation of carbohydrates.

Lactic acid bacteria are widely distributed in nature. They have been isolated from vacuum packed refrigerated beef, sourdoughs and traditional Indian fermented foods such as appam butter and vegetable pickle (Jamuna *et al*; 2004).

Lactic acid bacteria were realized as a group of bio preservative bacteria in the beginning of 1990's based on their interaction in foods. The bio preservative factors elaborated by LAB have been identified as peptides generally produced known as bacteriocins apart from lactic acid, acetic acid. The increasing demand for high quality safe processed food has created a niche for natural food preservatives. The ideal natural food preservation should fulfill a number of criteria such as acceptability, low toxicity, stability to processing and storage, economic viability. (Cintas *et al*; 1995; Cleveland *et al*; 2001).

2.2 Antimicrobial potential of lactic acid bacteria.

Lactic acid bacteria display a wide range of action of antimicrobial activities. Amongst these activities, the production of lactic acid and acetic acid is obviously the most important. However certain strains of lactic acid bacteria are further known to produce bioactive molecules such as ethanol, formic acid fatty acids, hydrogen peroxide, diacetyl, reutrin and reutericytin. Many strains also produce bacteriocin and bacteriocin-like molecules that display antibacterial activity, (De Vuyst and Vandamme,1994). Besides the production of bacteriocins some lactic acid are able to synthesize other antimicrobial peptides that may also contribute to food preservation and safety. For instance, strains of *Lactobacillus planetarium*, isolated from sourdough and grass silage display antifungal activity due to the production of organic acids, other low-molecular mass metabolites and /or cyclic dipeptides (Larvemicossa *et al*; 2000; storm *et al*; 2002; Schnurer and Magnusson, 2005).

2.3 Bacteriocins

Bacteriocins are small, ribosomally synthesized peptides or proteins which inhibit microorganisms that are usually closely related to producer strains (Oliveara *et al*;2008).

Bacteriocins were first discovered by Andrew Gratia in 1925 (Gratia, 2000) . He was involved in the process of searching for ways to kill bacteria which also resulted in the development of antibiotics and discovery of bacteriophage, all within a space of a few years. He called his first discovery a colicine because it killed E.coli. in contrast to the currently used antibiotics, bacteriocins are often considered more natural because they are thought to have been present in many of the foods eaten since ancient times (Cleveland *et al*; 2001).

2.4 CLASSIFICATION OF BACTERIOCINS

Most of the bacteriocins from lactic acid bacteria are cationic, hydrophobic or amphiphilic molecules composed of 20-60 amino acid residues (Nes and Holo,2000). Those bacteriocins are commonly classified into 4 groups that also include bacteriocins from other gram- positive bacteria (Klanenhammer 1993; Nes *et al*; 1996). These include:

1. Lantibiotics
2. Small (<10k Da) hydrophobic heat stable peptides.
3. Large (30k Da) heat labile proteins
4. Complex

2.4.1 Class 1 Bacteriocins (Lantibiotics)

Lantibiotics are a family of membrane active peptides that contain the unusual thio-ether, amino acids lanthionine and B- ethyl lanthionine as well as other modified amino acids ,such as dehydrated serine and threonine (Jung,199). Their distinguishing feature is the presence of post transitionally modified amino acid residues. The best example in this group is Nisin produced by *Lactococcus lactis subsp. lactis* (Altena *et al*. 2000).

2.4.2 Class 11 Bacteriocin (Small- Heat Stable peptide).

They are bioactive peptides, which do not contain any modified amino acid residues such as lanthionine. They are also further subdivided into 11a, 11b, 11c and 11d.

Class 11a Bacteriocins (Pediocin-link bacteriocins).

These are the largest subgroup and contain an N- terminal consensus sequence- Tyr- Gly- Asn- Gly- Val- Xaa-Cys across this group. The C- terminal is responsible for species- specific activity, causing cell leakage by permeabilizing the target cell wall.

Class 11a have a large potential for use in food preservation as well as medical applications, due to their strong antilisterial activity and broad range of activity. One example of class 11a bacteriocin is pediocin PA-I (Heng *et al*; 2007).

Class 11b (Two peptide Bacteriocins).

They require two different peptides for activity. The primary amino acid sequence of the peptides are different though each one is encoded by its own adjacent genes, only one immunity gene is needed (Cleveland *et al*; 2001). They form pores in membrane of target cells and disruption of the proton gradient of target cells.

Class 11c (Circular bacteriocins).

They have a wide range of effects on membrane permeability cell wall formation and pheromone actions of target cells (Cotter *et al*; 2006).

Class 11d (Single –peptides bacteriocins).

They are not post- translated modified and do not show the pediocin- like signature. The best example; of this group is the highly stable Gureocin A53. This bacteriocin is stable under highly acidic environment not affected by proteases and thermo-s resistant (Netz, *et al*; 2002). The most recently proposed sub class is the class 11e which encompasses those bacteriocins composed by 3 or 4 non pediocin like peptides.

The best example is Gvreocin A70,a four –peptide bacteriocin, highly active against *Listeria monocytogenes* with an enormous biotechnological application. (Oliveira, *et al*; 2001).

2.4.3 Class 111Bacteriocin (Large Heart Labile.

This class is subdivided into two classes, 111a (bacteriocin). It comprises of those peptides that kill bacterial cells by cell wall degradation, thus causing cell lysis. The best studied bacteriolysin is lyso staphin a 27KDa peptide that hydrolyzes several staphylococcus species aureus cell wall,principally staphylococcus aureus.

Subclass 111b in contrast, comprises

Those peptides that do not cause cell Lysis, killing the target cells by disrupting the membrane potential which cause ATP efflux.

2.4.4 Class iv Bcateriocin (complex bacteriocins).

They are defined as complex bacteriocins containing lipid or carbohydrate moieties. Coman *et al*; 2011.

2.5 TYPE OF BACTERIOCINS

Agrocin, Alveicin, carnocin, colicin, Curvaticin, divercin, enterocin, enterolysin, erwinocin, glycinecin, halocin, Lacticin, leucocin, mensentericin, Nisin, pediocin, planetariucin, subtilin, sulfolobicin, Vibriocin, warnercin (Cotter *et al*; 2006).

2.6 MODE OF ACTION OF BACTERIOCINS

Bacteriocin are a heterogenous group of anti-bacterial proteins that vary in spectrum of activity, mode of origin and biochemical properties. (Abee. *et al*; 1995).

They exert lethal activity through adsorption of specific receptors located on the external surface of sensitive bacteria, followed by metabolic biological and morphological changes resulting in the killing of such bacteria (Daw and falkner,1996).

Lethal action are of distinct phases namely, the initial combination of bacteriocin with specific receptor sites located on the cell wall of the sensitive organism which is followed by some sequence of events thereby leading to the death of the cell (Bakes *et al*;2004).

Class i bacteriocin may induce pore formation according to a wedged like model, and class ii bacteriocins may function by creating barrel store like pore or a carpet mechanism whereby peptides orient parallel to the membrane structure (Moll *et al*; 1999).

Nisin has been proposed to act on the cytoplasmic membranes of gram positive bacteria to cause lesions. Following Nisin treatment, whole or intact sensitive cells and membranes vesicle exhibit efflux of amino acids and cations. Loss of these substances depletes proton motive force, which ultimately interferes with cellular biosynthesis. This event results in collapse of the membrane potential and ultimately causes cellular death (Brul *et al*; 1999).

2.7 USES OF BACXTERIOCINS

Among the many different substance known to play a role in bacterial interaction, bacteriocins are the most specific and efficient antagonists. Bacteriocins comprise a large and functionally diverse family of toxins found in most microbial species.

They play a critical role in mediating microbial interactions and in maintaining microbial diversity. This diverse group of protein toxins has potential applications in human health, veterinary medicine, crop management, Agriculture, food preservation and Bioremediation (Riley *et al*; 2007).

2.7.1 BACTORIOCIN IN MEDICINE

Bacteriocins are of interest in medicine because they are made by non pathogenic bacteria that normally colonize the human body. Loss of these harmless bacteria following antibiotic use many allow opportunistic pathogen bacteria to invade the human body.

Bacteriocin have also been suggested as a cancer treatment, they have shown distinct promise as a diagnostic agent for some cancers (Farkas *et al*; 1995).

Bacteriocins also serve as replacement therapy for the generation of dental carries. A bacteriocin produce by streptococcus mutans strain 5H100 was originally based on its superior ability to colonize health, which was due to its production by bacxteriocin capable of killing all strains of S. mutans. Nisin has been used in the dental health care products as footh pastes and mouth washer for inhibition of dental carries and periodontal diseases application.

2.7.2 BACTERIOCINS IN FOOD PRESERVATION

Antibacterial metabolites of lactic acid bacteria and Bacillis SPP have potential as natural preservatives to control the growth of spoilage and pathogenic bacteria in food. Among them, bacteriocin is used as a preservative in food due to its health stability, wider PH tolerance and its proteolytic activity. Due to thermostability and PH tolerance, it can with stand heat and acidity/ alkalinity of food during storage condition (Sharm *et al*; 2009).

Many lactic acid bacteria used in food industry produce bacteriocin and these are a rich source of these natural inhibitors (Cintas *et al*; 2001). These bacteriocin have wide spread potential application in preservation of food for improving the safety and quality of foods. Indeed, bacteriocin may be viewed as an innate immunity

system which can be inbuilt into food system to protect them against contamination and (or outgrowth with undesirable flora.

Bacteriocin producing lactic acid bacteria have potential for the preservation of foods of plants origins especially minimally processed salads and fermented ones (Burt, 2004). Bacteriocins have been used as starter cultures in controlled and natural fermentation of meat, fish, vegetable and diary products (Leory and Devuyst, 2004).

2.7.3 BACTERIOGIN IN LIVESTOCK

The utilization of bacteriocin producing bacteria (BPB) in livestock has been evaluated as a potential alternative to antibiotics usage. Accordingly, the use of BPB in farm animals has increased the productivity, improved animal health and prevented the spread of human pathogens. Colicinogenic bacteria appear to be promising in controlling enterohemorrhagic E.coli in cattle and reducing the incidence of neonatal diarrhea caused by enterogenic E.coli in calves, microcin producing E.coli have been used to reduce salmonella carriage in poultry.

Lactacin produced by lactococcus lactis have been reported to be effective to reduce cow's mastitis caused by Staphylococcus aureus and staphylococcus dysgalactia. These findings indicate that utilization of bacteriocin will be a feasible antimicrobial intervention in livestock for the future (Diez- Gonzale z, 2007)

2.7.4 BACTERIOGIN AS FUNGICIDES

Apple scab causes by the fungus venturia inequalis is one of the most important apple disease worldwide. Control of scab has been reducing almost excessively on the use of fungicides .

Lactic acid bacterium was isolated from different environment and science for fungal activity and approximately 10% of the isolates show inhibitory activity and 40% showed strong activity against the indicator mould Aspergillus fumigatus (Magnusson *et al*; 2003).

MATERIALS AND METHOD

3.1 Materials

Materials used include., Test tubes, pipette, petridishes, distilled water, inoculating wire loop, bunsen burner, mccarthy bottles, slides, masking tape, microscope, incubator, autoclave, weighting balance, refrigerator, corkborer.

3.1.1 Media / Reagents Used

The media used were lactobacillus MRS (Mann Rogoso sharpse) agar, nutrient agar, Mueller Hinton agar, Oxidative fermentative based medium, glucose, mannitol, Gram's reagent, hydrogen peroxide.

3.2 Sample Collection

The whole cassava (manihot esculenta) used in this research work was obtained from one of the popular market in calabar (watt) in a sterile polythene bag and then conveyed to the microbiological laboratory for proper analysis.

3.3 Sample Preparation

The cassava were peeled, washed and soaked in water for 3days in a suitable container where fermentation takes place and the water was taken to the laboratory in a sterile container.

3.4 Microbiological Analysis

The pour plate technique was adopted for the analysis, 1ml of the sample was added to 9ml of sterile distilled water and 10-fold serial dilution was carried out. 1ml of the dilution (distilled water) from the dilution 10⁻⁵,10⁻⁶,10⁻⁷,10⁻⁸,10⁻⁹ were plated on to the centre of MRS Agar in duplicate in sterile petri dishes and incubated at 30^oc for 48hours.

3.4.1 Microbial Count

All colonies appearing at the end of the incubation period were counted and the result expressed as CFU /ml (colomy forming unit per ml).

3.5 PURIFICATION OF ISOLATES AND CULTURE PRESERVATION

Pure culture of lactobacilli isolates was obtained by repeatedly sub-culturing on fresh culture medium consisting of MRS Agar and maintained on a medium consisting of MRS broth with 12% (v/v) glycerol and incubated at 30^oc until growth becomes visible. The stock cultures were stored at 4^oc for subsequent use.

3.6 Identification Of Isolates

Each isolates are identified and characterized on the basics of cultural characteristics of colonies, microscopy and biochemical test.

3.6.1 Gram Staining

A drop of sterile distilled water was placed at the centre of a clean grease free glass slide. An innoculating wire loop was sterile by flaming and allowed to cool. A thin smear of innoculum was made on the slide and heat fixed.

It was then allowed to air dry, the smear was flooded with methyl violet solution for iminute drained off and rinsed with water. The smear was then flooded with gram's iodine for 1minute, drained off and rinsed with water, the slide was washed with 70% alcohol for 15 seconds and then rinsed with water.

The slide was then flooded with safranin red for 60 seconds, drained off and then rinsed with water. The slide was blotted dry, a drop of immersion oil under the microscope using x100 objective lens for identification of the morphology of isolates.

The principle of gram staining is based on the ability of the microorganism to retain the basic dye methyl violet after decolorization with alcohol.

Hence,they appear pink or red while gram positive bacteria are not decolourized and retain the primary colour and appear violet.

3.6.2 Motility

The principle of this test is to show if the isolated were mobile of crowery *et al.*, 1969 was used. A drop of water was placed on a clean slide. A troopful of the colouries was smeared on the slide a cover slide was placed gently and was observed runder the microscope using the oil immersion, objecticives x10 and x 40 objective lens.

3.7 Biochemical Test

3.7.1 Catalase Test

A loopful of the test organism was inoculated on a glass slide and 2-3 drops of hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) was added. The production of gas bubble shows that the organism is catalase shows negative result.

3.7.2 Citrate Test

Simmon's citrate ogar was used. The test organism were inoculated on to simmon's citrate slant and incubated for 24hours at 37⁰c, positive result shows a change in colour of the media from green to blue.

3.7.3 Oxidase Test

The principle of this test is to show if the organism contain oxidase enzymes that catalyzes the oxidation of cytochrome C. a piece of oxidase strip was used to rub on the lactic acid bacteria (LAB) isolate in a petridish. A change in colour to purple shows a positive result and no change shows a negative result.

3.7.4 Sugar Fermentation Test

This test is carried out to show the ability of the isolate to utilize different carbohydrates. The test carbohydrate inculde glucose, sucrose, lactose, mactose and mannitol this test was done by using 1% of based broth for five different sugars which inclde sucrose, lactose, glucose maltose and mannitol. An overnight broth culture of the test organism was inoculated into 0.05% peptone sugar water (sterile) using a sterile pasture pipette. Durham tubes were placed inside the test tubes and air bubble were removed, these tubes were incubated at room temperature. A colour change from green to yellow indicates acid production, thus a positive result for Agar fermentation. Similarly, if there is air space left inside the Durham's tube, gas is produced but if no space is left at the upper part of the invested Durham's tube gas is not produced.

3.7.5 Triple Sugar Iron (Tis) Agar Test

The TSI slant wa inculataed by streaking the slant surface using a zigzag streak pattern and then stabbing the agar deep with a straight inculating needle aseptically, it was then incubated for 18-24hours at 35⁰c for changes in the butt and on the slant. The tubes were then examined for the colour of the slant and butt for presence of darkening within the medium.

3.8 Pathogenic Bacteria Cultures

Pathogenic bacterial cultures example; escherichia coli, salmonella typhi, protein spp, staphylococcus aureus, pseudomonas aeruginosa, Klebsiella were gotten from the medical laboratory unit of the University of Calabar Teaching Hospital (UTCH) Calabar and used in bacteriocin screening procedures.

3.9 Preparation Of Culture Supernatant

Mrs broth media was weighed and put into a conical flask with distilled water measured and added to it. The mixture was shaken thoroughly to dissolve completely. 5ml was pipetted into test tubes and sterilized using autoclave at 121⁰c for 15mins. The tubes were allowed to cool and the subcultures LAB isolated using innoculating loop was picked and dissolved in the tubes which was labelled. The tubes were incubated at 37⁰c for 18-20hours it was centrifuged at 10,000rpm for 5mins to separate the cells from the supernatant and then the supernatant was adjusted to PH 6.5-7.0 with in NAOH (kilic *et al*; 1996).

3.10 Screening of Lactic Acid Bacteria for Bacterocin Productions

Antimicrobial activity of the bacteriocin producing pathogenic microorganisms was determined by agar well diffusion method (uhlman *et al.*,1992., kumvia *et al.*, 1998) Under aerobic condition, Mueller Hinton Agar was prepared and poured into sterile petri dishes and allowed to solidify. The target organism were dissolved in tubes containing sterile distilled water and using a sterile swab stick, the organisms was spread on the surface of the agar plates. Using a cork borer which plates. Using a cork boree which was flamed, wells were cut into the plates and 100ml of cell free culture supernatant fluid of the bacteriocin producing strains were pipetted into each well. Plates were kept at cool temperature for 2 hours and than incubated at 37⁰c for 24hours. The bacteriocin production was determined by measuring the diameter of the inhibition zones around the wells.

RESULT

4.1 ISOLATED AND CHARACTERIZATION OF LACTIC ACID BACTERIA.

Ten lactic acid bacteria were isolated from fermenting fufu but only five of the isolates were found to be bacteriocin producers and were effective against pathogenic and food spoilage organisms. Table 4.1 shows the morphology of the five LAB isolated on MRS agar.they were identified based on their shape, pigmentation consistency, colony surface and elevation. Table 4,2 shows the biochemical characteristics of the five isolate.

They were all catalase negative and oxidase negative, they utilized glucose fermentatively producing acid with no gas but they did not utilized mannitol. Gram reaction of the five isolates of LAB when viewed under the microscope using x100 magnification with oil immersion appeared purple in colour to stain. They werelong and short rods.

4.2 PRODUCTION OF BACTERIOCIN

The preparation of culture supernatant in MRS broth of the five LAB isolates for antimicrobial activity is shown in plate 4:1. The supernatant was separated from the cells and used for screening for bacteriocin production. Table 4:3 Shows the screening of LAB iisolates for antimicrobial activity against food spoilage and pathogenic organisms such as *staphillococcus aureus*, *Escherichiacoli*, *proteus spp.* *Pseudomonas aeuyinosa*, *bacillus spp*, and *salmonella typhi*. It showed that they have potential for bacteriocin production by plate 4.2 shows bacteriocin production froms isolates. The LAB isolates were sensitive to *pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Stapillococcus aureus*, *proteus*, *escherichia coli* and were resisted by *salmonella typhi*, *klebsiella* and *Bacillus spp.* Their zones of inhibition were measured and recorded in table 4:3.

5.1 DISCUSSION

Bacteriocins produced by lactic acid bacteria (LAB) have the potentials to cover a very broad field of application including both the food industry and medical sectors. The result from the production of bacteriocin from fermented food production fufu, based on the morphological and biochemical test, identified the isolates as belonging to lactic acid bacteria (LAB) group, *Lactobacillus* spp. This bacteria, effectively control the microbial ecology of germination by consuming the glucose and fructose present and producing lactic acid, thus lactic acid bacteria are responsible for fermentation process. The bacteriocin produced from the fermented fufu produced inhibition zone against the tested organisms. However, it was generally observed that bacteriocin from the producer organisms had no inhibitory effect on the organisms producing it.

From this result, it could be concluded that locally fermented food product fufu contained lactic acid bacteria (LAB). The antimicrobial activity produced by the bacteriocin produced in this research could act as a potential barrier to inhibit the growth of pathogenic and food spoilage organisms. They can also have their use as started cultures for traditional fermented foods with a view of improving the hygiene and safety of the food product so produced.

5.2 CONCLUSION

This research work revealed that bacteriocin from *Lactobacillus* spp isolated from natural lactic acid fermentation of fufu (cassava) possess a wide spectrum of inhibitory activity against *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus* spp. Therefore, it has a potential for application as a bio preservative in different food products as such or in combination with other preservation methods. Since lactic acid fermentation is employed mostly for development of products especially for flavour and taste of the fermented products, the production of bacteriocin in such products assumes more significance as bio preservative. With respect to medical applications, bacteriocins produced by lactic acid bacteria might play a role during in vivo interactions occurring in the human gastro intestinal tract, hence contributing to get health.

5.3 RECOMMENDATION

Since fermentation is the cheapest method of biopreservation, industrialist should encourage its use and bacteriocins should be used in food preservation, since it permits the application of less severe heat treatments, without compromising food safety and it inhibits a wide range of gram positive bacteria and inhibit the growth of similar or closely related strains.

Table:4:1

Showing the plate count and preliminary characteristics of lactobacillus spp from fermenting fufu.

Sample	Colonycfu/ml	Elevation	Shape	Pigmentation	Colony surface	Texture	Grams Reaction
10-4	20x10 ⁴	Raised	Circular	Creamy	Smooth	Mucoid	Gram positive rods in chain
10-5	15x10 ⁵	Flat	Circular	Creamy	Smooth	Glossy	Gram positive rods in chain
10-6	11x10 ⁵	Raised	Circular	Creamy	Smooth	Mucoid	Gram positive rods in chain
10-7	23x10 ⁷	Raised	Circular	Creamy	Smooth	Glossy	Gram positive rods in chain
10-8	30x10 ⁸	Flat	Circular	Creamy	Smooth	mucoid	Gram positive rods in chain

Table: 4:2 Showing biochemical characterization of lactobacillus spp from fermenting fufu.

BIOCHEMICAL REACTION

Colony code	Lac	Many	Glu	Cit	Ind	Oxid	Mot	H ₂ S	Gas	Slope	Butt	Cat	Probable organism
fs 1	+	+	+	-	nr	-	-	-	-	y	y	-	lactobacillus spp
fs 2	+	+	+	-	nr	-	-	-	-	y	y	-	lactobacillus spp
fs 3	+	+	+	-	nr	-	-	-	-	y	y	-	lactobacillus spp
fs 4	+	+	+	-	nr	-	-	-	-	y	y	-	lactobacillus spp
fs 5	+	+	+	-	nr	-	-	-	-	y	y	-	lactobacillus spp

KEYS

LAC	-	Lactose Fermentation Test
MANN	-	Mannitol Utilization Test
GLU	-	Glucose Fermentation test
CIT	-	Citrate test
OXID	-	Oxidase test
MOT	-	Motility test
H ₂ S	-	Hydrogen Sulphide test
CAT	-	Catalase Test
NR	-	Not required
Y	-	Yellow

Table 4.3 showing the effect of bacteriocins production by LAB isolates on test organisms

Colony Code/Testorganisms	FS1	FS2	FS3	FS4	FS5
Staphylococcus	2mm	3mm	3mm	-	-

aureus					
Klebsiella	-	-	-	-	-
Pseudomonas aeruginosa	2mm	4mm	4mm	2mm	3mm
Proteus	3mm	-	-	2mm	2mm
Escherichia	3mm	-	2mm	2mm	4mm
Salmonella typhi	-	-	-	-	-
Bacillus Spp.	-	-	-	-	-

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APPENDIX 1

COMPOSITION OF MEDIA USED

Lactobacillus MRS AGAR

Constituent	weight (gm)
Dextrose	20
Beef extract	10.0
Yeast extract	5.0
Tween 80	1.0
Sodium acetate	5.0
Disodium phosphate	2.0
Ammonium citrate	2.0
Magnesium sulphate	0.1
Magnesium sulphate	0.05
PH	6.5±0.2 at 25°C

Nutrient Agar

Constituent	weight (g/l)
Peptone	5.0
Yeast extract	3.0
Sodium chloride	8.0
Agar	12.0

PH 7.4

Mueller Hinton Agar

Constituent	weight (g/l)
Agar	17.0
Casein Acidhydrolysate	17.5
Beef extract	2.0
Starch	1.5

APPENDIX 11

Composition of reagent used

Gram stain reagent	
Crystal Violet (primary stain)	2.0g
Crystal violet (85%dye)	20ml
Gram's iodine(mordant)	
Iodine crystal	1g
Potassium iodine	2g
Distill water	300ml
Safranin (counter stain)	
Safranin	2.5g
75% ethyl alcohol	100ml.

Sugar Fermentation Test Medium (Basal Medium)

Constituent	weight (g/l)
Peptone water	4.5
Nacl	1.5
Casein	6.0
Dipotassium hydrogen orthophosphate	0.18
Phenol red	0.002
Distill water	300

Simmon citrate

Constituent	weight
Magnesium sulphate	0.2
Ammonium diahydrogen	1.0
Dipotassium phosphate	1.0
Sodium citrate	2.0
Sodium chloride	5.0
Bromothymol blue	0.08
Agar	15.0

Catalse test

Distilled water	100ml
Hydrogen peroxide	3g
Fat	28%
Protein	26%
Lactase	38%
Mineral	5.5%
Moisture	3%
Lecithin	0.2g
Vitamin A	8331 μ
Vitamin D3	8521 μ
Caloric Content	214kg.

Indole test

Peptone	5.0g
Dextrose	5.0g
Phosphate buffer	5.0g
PH	7.5

APPENDIX 111

Description of preparation of media and reagent used.

MRS BROTH

55.0g of the powdered medium was weighed and dissolved in one liter of distilled water in a conical flask.

It was then sterilized by autoclaving at 121⁰c for 15minutes.

Note: In preparing MRS Agar, agar-agar was weighed and added to the MRS broth before sterilization.

Nutrient Agar

28.0 g of the power was dissolved in one liter of distilled water, stirred and boiled to disslove completely. It was then autoclaved at 121⁰c for 15 minutes.

Mueller Hinton Agar

38.0g of the powdered medium was dissloved in one liter of distilled water in a conical flask. It was sterilized by autoclaving at 121⁰c for 15 minutes.

Simmon Citrate Agar

24g of the powder was dissolved in one litre of distilled water and soaked for is minutes and boiled completely and then sterilized by autoclaving for 15 minutes at 121⁰c.

Sugar utilization test medium: The medium was properly mixed and dispensed into 10ml test tubes. 0.5g of each of the sugar was put into each tube so that a tube contained only one type of sugar. A Durham tube was put in an invented position into ech test tube. All the tube were then sterilzed by autoclaving at 121⁰c for 15 minutes. The tubes were then allowed to cool before inoculation.

How to Cite this Work.

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